

MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF TWELVE FINGER ULCER DISEASE

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Relevance of the topic: Metabolic syndrome is a chronic and acute metabolic disorder in the human body, and recently there has been a lot of talk about metabolic syndrome (MS). Why is this cash register dangerous? Because it can lead to the development of many serious diseases, such as atherosclerosis, heart attack, stroke, kidney failure, cancer, and the most common is diabetes.

The purpose of the work: the purpose of the work was to determine the morphological changes in the duodenum in patients with metabolic syndrome.

Results obtained: 70-80% of the patients with metabolic syndrome were studied by gender, and it was found that 12-finger ulcer disease was diagnosed as a disease, compared to other chronic diseases.

During the histological examination of 12 intestinal macropreparations brought from medical institutions located on the territory of the province to the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy, it was found that the histopreparations often have chronic hypoxia, a violation of the integrity of the mucous membrane.

Conclusions: in conclusion, it can be said that 12 duodenal ulcers, which are more common in women compared to men, are complicated by ulcers in the bulb part, antral part of the stomach, body of the stomach, lesser curvature of the stomach, cardial part of the stomach.

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